
ON SIERPIŃSKI AND RIESEL REPDIGITS AND REPINTEGERS

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Abstract

For positive integers $b \geq 2$, $k < b$, and t , we say that an integer $k_b^{(t)}$ is a b -repdigit if $k_b^{(t)}$ can be expressed as the digit k repeated t times in base- b representation, i.e., $k_b^{(t)} = k(b^t - 1)/(b - 1)$. In the case of $k = 1$, we say that $1_b^{(t)}$ is a b -repunit. In this article, we investigate the existence of b -repdigits and b -repunits among the sets of Sierpiński numbers and Riesel numbers. A Sierpiński number is defined as an odd integer k for which $k \cdot 2^n + 1$ is composite for all positive integers n and Riesel numbers are similarly defined for the expression $k \cdot 2^n - 1$.

1. Introduction

In 1956, Riesel demonstrated that $509203 \cdot 2^n - 1$ is composite for all positive integers n [16]. He further proved the existence of infinitely many odd integers k for which $k \cdot 2^n - 1$ is composite for all positive integers n . Similarly, in 1960, Sierpiński showed that there are infinitely many odd integers k such that $k \cdot 2^n + 1$ is composite for all positive integers n [17]. These numbers are now known as Riesel numbers and Sierpiński numbers, respectively. To date, 509203 is the smallest known Riesel number. The smallest known Sierpiński number, discovered by John Selfridge in 1962, is 78557. We note that Selfridge never published his discovery.

Building on the foundational work of Riesel and Sierpiński, researchers have explored the presence of Riesel numbers and Sierpiński numbers in various integer sequences. Such investigations have considered Riesel numbers and Sierpiński numbers among binomial coefficients [1], polygonal numbers [2, 3], Lucas numbers [4], Carmichael numbers [6], perfect j -th powers [9, 11], Ruth-Aaron pairs [8], Narayana's cow sequence [12], and Fibonacci numbers [15].

For positive integers $b \geq 2$, $k < b$, and t , we say that an integer $k_b^{(t)}$ is a *b-repdigit* if $k_b^{(t)}$ can be expressed as the digit k repeated t times in base- b representation, i.e., $k_b^{(t)} = k(b^t - 1)/(b - 1)$. In the case of $k = 1$, we say that $1_b^{(t)}$ is a *b-repunit*. Repunits and repdigits have been topics of studies in the literature since 1966 [7, 18]. Extending the definition of *b-repdigits*, for any positive integer k , we say that an integer $k_b^{(t)}$ is a *b-repinteger* if $k_b^{(t)}$ can be expressed as k repeated t times in base- b representation, i.e., $k_b^{(t)} = k(b^{\ell t} - 1)/(b^\ell - 1)$, where $\ell = \lfloor \log_b(k) \rfloor + 1$. In this article, we investigate the existence of Sierpiński numbers and Riesel numbers in *b-repunits*, *b-repdigits*, and *b-repintegers*.

In Section 3, we provide an argument to suggest the nonexistence of 2-repdigit Sierpiński numbers. In light of this, the following questions are the motivation for the other results in this paper.

Question 1.1. What is the smallest integer $\beta_1 \geq 2$ for which there exists a β_1 -repunit Sierpiński number?

Question 1.2. What is the smallest integer $\beta_2 \geq 2$ for which there exists a β_2 -repdigit Sierpiński number?

Question 1.3. What is the smallest positive integer κ for which there exists a positive integer t such that $\kappa_2^{(t)}$ is a 2-repinteger Sierpiński number?

We will establish the existence of β_1 , β_2 , and κ , and show that $\beta_1 \leq 147$, $\beta_2 \leq 87$, and $\kappa \leq 18107$ by Corollary 3.12, Theorem 3.9, and Theorem 3.5, respectively. Similar questions can be asked about Riesel numbers.

Question 1.4. What is the smallest integer $\beta'_1 \geq 2$ for which there exists a β'_1 -repunit Riesel number?

Question 1.5. What is the smallest integer $\beta'_2 \geq 2$ for which there exists a β'_2 -repdigit Riesel number?

Question 1.6. What is the smallest positive integer κ' for which there exists a positive integer t such that $\kappa_2'^{(t)}$ is a 2-repinteger Riesel number?

Analogous results for Riesel numbers are $\beta'_1 \leq 16518444216571$, $\beta'_2 \leq 180$, and $\kappa' \leq 18107$ by Corollary 3.14, Theorem 3.10, and Theorem 3.6, respectively.

2. The Covering System Method

Finding Sierpiński numbers and Riesel numbers has historically involved the use of covering systems of the integers. In this section, we demonstrate the method that is commonly used to find these numbers.

A *covering system of integers*, often referred to simply as a *covering system*, is a finite collection of congruences such that every integer satisfies at least one of the congruences in the collection. One can take $\mathcal{C}_0 = \{0 \pmod{3}, 1 \pmod{3}, 2 \pmod{3}\}$ for a simple example of a covering system. The collection $\mathcal{C}_1 = \{0 \pmod{2}, 0 \pmod{3}, 1 \pmod{4}, 3 \pmod{8}, 11 \pmod{12}, 7 \pmod{24}\}$ is a less trivial example of a covering system. We will use this covering system to demonstrate our process for generating Sierpiński numbers and Riesel numbers.

Let n be a fixed positive integer. Since \mathcal{C}_1 is a covering system, n must satisfy at least one of the congruences in the covering. Suppose $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Then $n = 2w$ for some integer w and

$$\begin{aligned} k \cdot 2^n + 1 &= k \cdot 2^{2w} + 1 \\ &= k \cdot 4^w + 1 \\ &\equiv k + 1 \pmod{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if $k \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ and $k > 0$, then $k \cdot 2^n + 1$ is divisible by 3 and is therefore composite since $k \cdot 2^n + 1 > 3$ for all positive $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Using this technique, we go through each of the congruences in \mathcal{C}_1 to get the following:

$$\begin{aligned} n \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ and } k \equiv 2 \pmod{3} &\implies k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \\ n \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \text{ and } k \equiv 6 \pmod{7} &\implies k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} \\ n \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \text{ and } k \equiv 2 \pmod{5} &\implies k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{5} \\ n \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \text{ and } k \equiv 2 \pmod{17} &\implies k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{17} \quad (1) \\ n \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \text{ and } k \equiv 11 \pmod{13} &\implies k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{13} \\ n \equiv 7 \pmod{24} \text{ and } k \equiv 32 \pmod{241} &\implies k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{241}. \end{aligned}$$

To ensure that k is odd, we further require $k \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Note that the system of congruences on k has infinitely many solutions by the Chinese remainder theorem.

To ensure that $k \cdot 2^n + 1$ is not in the set $\{3, 7, 5, 17, 13, 241\}$, we may select k to be sufficiently large, thus yielding a Sierpiński number.

It is important to note that each of the implications in Equation (1) can be written as

$$n \equiv r_j \pmod{m_j} \text{ and } k \equiv -2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j} \implies k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_j}, \quad (2)$$

where $r_j \pmod{m_j}$ is a congruence in our covering system and p_j is a prime divisor of $2^{m_j} - 1$. We use a similar set of implications to construct Riesel numbers:

$$n \equiv r_j \pmod{m_j} \text{ and } k \equiv 2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j} \implies k \cdot 2^n - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_j}. \quad (3)$$

To construct Sierpiński numbers and Riesel numbers from a generic covering system $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j} : 1 \leq j \leq \tau\}$, we want $p_i \neq p_j$ for each $1 \leq i < j \leq \tau$. The following theorem of Bang [5] is a useful tool to help establish this criteria. For a positive integer m , we call a prime p a *primitive prime divisor* of $2^m - 1$ if p divides $2^m - 1$ and p does not divide $2^\mu - 1$ for any positive integers $\mu < m$.

Theorem 2.1 (Bang). *For each integer $m \geq 2$ with $m \neq 6$, there exists a primitive prime divisor of $2^m - 1$.*

3. Main Results

Note that if k is a Sierpiński number found using the covering system method described in Section 2, then $k \cdot 2^n + 1$ is divisible by one of the primes in the set $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_\tau\}$. This observation was known to Erdős, who made the following conjecture [13].

Conjecture 3.1. *If k is a Sierpiński number, then the smallest prime divisor of $k \cdot 2^n + 1$ is bounded as n tends to infinity.*

Although this conjecture has not been disproven, there are a few papers that suggest that it may be false [9, 14]. If Conjecture 3.1 is true, then the following theorem suggests the nonexistence of 2-repdigit Sierpiński numbers. We note that the argument in the proof of Theorem 3.2 cannot be easily modified to provide insight on the existence of 2-repdigit Riesel numbers.

Theorem 3.2. *The covering system method in Section 2 cannot yield a 2-repdigit Sierpiński number.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j} : 1 \leq j \leq \tau\}$ be a covering system and let L be the least common multiple of the moduli in \mathcal{C} . Then L must satisfy at least one

of the congruences of \mathcal{C} , and it follows that $r_j = 0$ for some $1 \leq j \leq \tau$. Thus, to satisfy Equation (2), we need $k_2^{(t)} \equiv -2^{-r_j} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_j}$. Note that if $k_2^{(t)}$ is a 2-repdigit, then $k = 1$ and $k_2^{(t)} = 2^t - 1$ for some positive integer t . Therefore, we need $2^t - 1 \equiv -1 \pmod{p_j}$, which is impossible since $p_j \neq 2$ for each $1 \leq j \leq \tau$. \square

While Theorem 3.2 suggests that it is difficult to find 2-repdigit Sierpiński numbers, the following theorem establishes the existence of b -repinteger Sierpiński numbers for any $b \geq 2$. A similar proof can establish an analogous result on b -repinteger Riesel numbers, as stated in Theorem 3.4.

Theorem 3.3. *Let k be a Sierpiński number constructed using the covering system method in Section 2. Then for every integer $b \geq 2$, there exist infinitely many positive integers t such that $k_b^{(t)}$ is a Sierpiński number.*

Theorem 3.4. *Let k be a Riesel number constructed using the covering system method in Section 2. Then for every integer $b \geq 2$, there exist infinitely many positive integers t such that $k_b^{(t)}$ is a Riesel number.*

Proof of Theorem 3.3. Let $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j}\}$ be the covering system that produces k as a Sierpiński number. Further, let p_j be a primitive prime divisor of $2^{m_j} - 1$ such that $k \equiv -2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ for each j . Let t be a positive integer such that $t \equiv 1 \pmod{\text{ord}_{p_j}(b)}$ for each p_j that does not divide b , where $\text{ord}_{p_j}(b)$ denotes the order of b modulo p_j . We claim that $k_b^{(t)} \equiv k \pmod{p_j}$ for all j . Note that the congruence in the claim holds trivially if p_j divides b , and if p_j does not divide b , then $k_b^{(t)} \equiv k(b^\ell - 1)/(b^\ell - 1) \equiv k \pmod{p_j}$, where $\ell = \lfloor \log_b(k) \rfloor + 1$.

By Equation (2), when $n \equiv r_j \pmod{m_j}$, we have $k_b^{(t)} \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv k \cdot 2^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_j}$. Also, we have $k_b^{(t)} \cdot 2^n + 1 \geq k \cdot 2^n + 1 > p_j$. Since \mathcal{C} is a covering system, this ensures that $k_b^{(t)} \cdot 2^n + 1$ is composite for all positive integers n . Further requiring $t \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ ensures that $k_b^{(t)}$ is an odd integer, and thus a Sierpiński number. \square

Besides establishing the existence of infinitely many b -repinteger Sierpiński numbers for any $b \geq 2$, Theorem 3.3 also provides a bound to the answer to Question 1.3 by showing that $\kappa \leq 78557$, the smallest known Sierpiński number. We further improve this bound on κ to $\kappa \leq 18107$ via the following theorem.

Theorem 3.5. *Let $t \equiv 25 \pmod{56}$. Then $18107_2^{(t)}$ is a 2-repinteger Sierpiński number.*

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(r_j, m_j, p_j) : 1 \leq j \leq 6\} \\ & = \{(0, 2, 3), (0, 3, 7), (1, 4, 5), (3, 8, 17), (11, 12, 13), (7, 24, 241)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j} : 1 \leq j \leq 6\}$ is the covering system provided in Equation (1). This establishes that a positive integer k is a Sierpiński number if $k \equiv 8007257 \pmod{11184810}$, where $11184810 = 2 \cdot \prod_{j=1}^6 p_j$. Hence, it remains to show that $18107_2^{(t)}$ satisfies this congruence.

Notice that $\ell = \lfloor \log_2(18107) \rfloor + 1 = 15$. For $p \in \{3, 7, 5, 17, 13, 241\}$, we have $2^{15 \cdot 56} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Therefore, when $t \equiv 25 \pmod{56}$, we have $2^{15 \cdot t} \equiv 2^{15 \cdot 25} \pmod{p}$. With this, we can check computationally that $18107_2^{(t)} = 18107 \cdot (2^{15 \cdot t} - 1) / (2^{15} - 1) \equiv 8007257 \pmod{p}$ for $p \in \{2, 3, 7, 5, 17, 13, 241\}$, establishing the desired congruence. \square

Analogously, for Question 1.6, Theorem 3.4 provides a bound $\kappa' \leq 509203$, the smallest known Riesel number, and this bound on κ' is improved to $\kappa' \leq 18107$ by the following theorem. We present this theorem without a proof, as it will follow as a corollary to Theorems 3.5 and 4.6.

Theorem 3.6. *Let $t \equiv 31 \pmod{56}$. Then $18107_2^{(t)}$ is a 2-repinteger Riesel number.*

Noting that a b -repinteger $k_b^{(t)} = k(b^{\ell t} - 1) / (b^\ell - 1)$ with $\ell = \lfloor \log_b(k) \rfloor + 1$ is a b^ℓ -repdigit and recalling that 78557 and 509203 are the smallest known Sierpiński number and Riesel number, respectively, we have the following corollaries of Theorems 3.3 and 3.4.

Corollary 3.7. *For all integers $b > 78557$, there exist infinitely many b -repdigit Sierpiński numbers.*

Corollary 3.8. *For all integers $b > 509203$, there exist infinitely many b -repdigit Riesel numbers.*

Corollary 3.7 provides a bound to the answer to Question 1.2 by showing that $\beta_2 \leq 78858$, and we significantly improve this bound to $\beta_2 \leq 87$ via the next theorem. Similarly, we establish in Theorem 3.10 that $\beta'_2 \leq 180$.

Theorem 3.9. *Let $b \geq 2$ be an integer with $b \equiv 87 \pmod{11184810}$ and let t be a positive integer with $t \equiv 59 \pmod{120}$. Then $41_b^{(t)}$ is a b -repdigit Sierpiński number.*

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(r_j, m_j, p_j) : 1 \leq j \leq 6\} \\ & = \{(0, 2, 3), (2, 3, 7), (1, 4, 5), (7, 8, 17), (7, 12, 13), (3, 24, 241)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j} : 1 \leq j \leq 6\}$ is a covering system. We claim that $41_b^{(t)} \equiv -2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ for all $1 \leq j \leq 6$. Note that the congruence in the claim

holds when $j = 1$ since $p_1 = 3$ divides b . For $2 \leq j \leq 6$, the congruence holds since $41(87^{59} - 1)/(87 - 1) \equiv -2^{r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ and $87^{120} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$. Therefore, $41_b^{(t)}$ is a Sierpiński number by Equation (2). \square

Theorem 3.10. *Let $b \geq 2$ be an integer with $b \equiv 180 \pmod{11184810}$ and let t be a positive integer with $t \equiv 171 \pmod{240}$. Then $101_b^{(t)}$ is a b -repdigit Riesel number.*

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} \{(r_j, m_j, p_j) : 1 \leq j \leq 6\} \\ = \{(1, 2, 3), (2, 3, 7), (0, 4, 5), (2, 8, 17), (10, 12, 13), (6, 24, 241)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j} : 1 \leq j \leq 6\}$ is a covering system. We claim that $101_b^{(t)} \equiv 2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ for all $1 \leq j \leq 6$. Note that the congruence in the claim holds when $j \in \{1, 3\}$ since $p_1 = 3$ and $p_3 = 5$ divide b . For $j \in \{2, 4, 5, 6\}$, the congruence holds since $101(180^{171} - 1)/(180 - 1) \equiv 2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ and $171^{240} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$. Therefore, $101_b^{(t)}$ is a Riesel number by Equation (3). \square

The next theorem provides sufficient conditions on b for which there exist b -repunit Sierprinski numbers, and its corollary establishes $\beta_1 \leq 147$.

Theorem 3.11. *Let τ be an integer such that $2^{2^\tau} - 1$ has at least two distinct primitive prime divisors. For each $1 \leq j \leq \tau$, let p_j be a primitive prime divisor of $2^{2^j} - 1$, and let*

$$\ell_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } b \equiv 0 \pmod{p_j}; \\ p_j & \text{if } b \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}; \text{ and} \\ \text{ord}_{p_j}(b) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, let $L = \text{lcm}(2, \ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_\tau)$, and let q be a primitive prime divisor of $2^{2^\tau} - 1$ with $q \neq p_\tau$. For any integer $b > 2$ with $b \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$, there exist infinitely many b -repunit Sierpiński numbers provided that b satisfies one of the following:

- (i) $b \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ and q does not divide L ;
- (ii) $b \not\equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ and there exists an integer t such that $(b^t - 1)/(b - 1) \equiv -1 \pmod{q}$ and $t \equiv 1 \pmod{L}$.

Proof. Notice that $\{2^{j-1} \pmod{2^j} : 1 \leq j \leq \tau\} \cup \{0 \pmod{2^\tau}\}$ is a covering system. Let t be an integer such that $t \equiv 1 \pmod{L}$. We claim that $1_b^{(t)} \equiv -2^{-2^{j-1}} \pmod{p_j}$ for all $1 \leq j \leq \tau$, which is equivalent to $1_b^{(t)} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$ since $2^{2^{j-1}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_j}$. Note that the congruence in the claim holds trivially if $b \equiv 0 \pmod{p_j}$. If $b \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$, then $1_b^{(t)} = \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} b^i \equiv t \equiv 1 \pmod{L}$, implying that $1_b^{(t)} \equiv 1$

(mod p_j) since $\ell_j = p_j$. Otherwise, $b^t \equiv b \pmod{p_j}$ since $\ell_j = \text{ord}_{p_j}(b)$, which again implies that $1_b^{(t)} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$.

In view of Equation (2), for $1_b^{(t)}$ to be a Sierpiński number, it remains to ensure that $1_b^{(t)} \equiv -2^{-0} \equiv -1 \pmod{q}$. If $b \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ and q does not divide L , we may impose an additional restriction that $t \equiv -1 \pmod{q}$. Hence, $1_b^{(t)} = \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} b^i \equiv t \equiv -1 \pmod{q}$. Otherwise, condition (ii) yields our desired congruence. \square

Corollary 3.12. *Let $b > 2$ be such that $b \equiv \mathfrak{b} \pmod{641}$ for some $\mathfrak{b} \in \{1, 147, 265, 378\}$ and $b \not\equiv 1 \pmod{5}$. Then there are infinitely many b -repunit Sierpiński numbers.*

Proof. Consider the covering system $\{2^{j-1} \pmod{2^j} : 1 \leq j \leq 6\} \cup \{0 \pmod{2^6}\}$. Let $p_1 = 3, p_2 = 5, p_3 = 17, p_4 = 257, p_5 = 65537, p_6 = 6700417$, and $q = 641$. Further, let $L_0 = \text{lcm}(2, p_1, p_3, p_4, p_5, p_6, p_1 - 1, p_2 - 1, p_3 - 1, p_4 - 1, p_5 - 1, p_6 - 1)$, which is a multiple of L since $b \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p_2}$ and $\text{ord}_{p_j}(b)$ divides $p_j - 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq 6$. Note that q does not divide L since q does not divide L_0 . Therefore, if $b \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$, then part (i) of Theorem 3.11 is satisfied.

Now suppose that $b \not\equiv 1 \pmod{q}$. Then $\mathfrak{b} \in \{147, 265, 278\}$ and $\text{ord}_q(b) = 640$. Let

$$t \equiv \begin{cases} 385 \pmod{640} & \text{if } \mathfrak{b} = 147; \\ 513 \pmod{640} & \text{if } \mathfrak{b} = 265; \\ 257 \pmod{640} & \text{if } \mathfrak{b} = 378 \end{cases}$$

so that $(b^t - 1)/(b - 1) \equiv -1 \pmod{q}$. Note that $\text{gcd}(640, L_0) = 2^7$ and $t \equiv 1 \pmod{2^7}$. Hence, we may apply the Chinese remainder theorem to ensure that $t \equiv 1 \pmod{L}$. Therefore, part (ii) of Theorem 3.11 is satisfied. \square

The next theorem is a Riesel analog to Theorem 3.11. Its corollary establishes $\beta'_1 \leq 16518444216571$.

Theorem 3.13. *Let τ be an integer such that $2^{2^\tau} - 1$ has at least two distinct primitive prime divisors. Let p_j be a primitive prime divisor of $2^{2^j} - 1$ for each $1 \leq j \leq \tau$, q be a primitive prime divisor of $2^{2^\tau} - 1$ with $q \neq p_\tau$, and $P = p_1 p_2 \cdots p_\tau$. For any integer $b > 2$ with $b \equiv 1 \pmod{P}$, there exist infinitely many b -repunit Riesel numbers provided that b satisfies one of the following:*

- (i) $b \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$;
- (ii) $b \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$;
- (iii) $b \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}, b \not\equiv 1 \pmod{q}$, and $\text{gcd}(P, \text{ord}_q(b)) = 1$.

Proof. Notice that $\{2^{j-1} \pmod{2^j} : 1 \leq j \leq \tau\} \cup \{0 \pmod{2^\tau}\}$ is a covering system. Let t be an integer such that $t \equiv -1 \pmod{P}$. Since $b \equiv 1 \pmod{P}$, we have $1_b^{(t)} = \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} b^i \equiv t \equiv -1 \equiv 2^{-2^{j-1}} \pmod{p_j}$ for all $1 \leq j \leq \tau$.

In view of Equation (3), for $1_b^{(t)}$ to be a Riesel number, it remains to ensure that $1_b^{(t)} \equiv 2^{-0} \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$. Note that this congruence trivially holds if $b \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$. If $b \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$, then since q does not divide P , we may impose an additional restriction that $t \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$, which implies that $1_b^{(t)} = \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} b^i \equiv t \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$. If we are under condition (iii), then we may impose an additional restriction that $t \equiv 1 \pmod{\text{ord}_q(b)}$. In this case, $1_b^{(t)} = (b^t - 1)/(b - 1) \equiv (b - 1)/(b - 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$. \square

Corollary 3.14. *Let $b \equiv 16518444216571 \pmod{18446744073709551615}$. Then there are infinitely many b -repunit Riesel numbers.*

Proof. Consider the covering system $\{2^{j-1} \pmod{2^j} : 1 \leq j \leq 6\} \cup \{0 \pmod{2^6}\}$. Let $p_1 = 3, p_2 = 5, p_3 = 17, p_4 = 257, p_5 = 65537, p_6 = 641$, and $q = 6700417$. Then $P = p_1 p_2 \cdots p_6 = 2753074036095, Pq = 18446744073709551615$, and $b \equiv 1 \pmod{P}$. Furthermore, $b \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}, b \not\equiv 1 \pmod{q}$, and $\text{gcd}(P, \text{ord}_q(b)) = \text{gcd}(P, \text{ord}_q(16518444216571)) = 1$. \square

4. Concluding Remarks

Besides improving the bounds to the answers to Questions 1.1 through 1.6, there are a few other interesting directions for investigation. For instance, for positive integers $b \geq 2, k$, and t , we may define a b -repstring as $k_b^{(z;t)} = k(b^{(z+\ell)t} - 1)/(b^{z+\ell} - 1)$ for any nonnegative integer z , where $\ell = \lfloor \log_b(k) \rfloor + 1$. Repstrings are a generalization of repintegers since $k_b^{(0;t)} = k_b^{(t)}$, while in general, repstrings allow us to insert z zeroes between repeated occurrences of k . For example, 1001001 is a repstring with $b = 10, k = 1, t = 3, z = 2$, and $\ell = 1$. We may ask the following questions on b -repstrings.

Question 4.1. What is the smallest positive integer $\tilde{\kappa}$ for which there exists a nonnegative integer z and a positive integer t such that $\tilde{\kappa}_2^{(z;t)}$ is a 2-repstring Sierpiński number?

Question 4.2. What is the smallest positive integer $\tilde{\kappa}'$ for which there exists a nonnegative integer z and a positive integer t such that $\tilde{\kappa}'_2^{(z;t)}$ is a 2-repstring Riesel number?

The following two theorems establish that $\tilde{\kappa} \leq 659$ and $\tilde{\kappa}' \leq 659$.

Theorem 4.3. *Let $t \equiv \mathfrak{t} \pmod{2730}$ for some $\mathfrak{t} \in \{131, 1361\}$. Then $659_2^{(2;t)}$ is a 2-repstring Sierpiński number.*

The proof of Theorem 4.3 resembles that of Theorem 3.5. In particular, when $t \equiv 131 \pmod{2730}$, we can use

$$\begin{aligned} &\{(r_j, m_j, p_j) : 1 \leq j \leq 6\} \\ &= \{(1, 2, 3), (2, 3, 7), (0, 4, 5), (6, 8, 17), (10, 12, 13), (18, 24, 241)\} \end{aligned}$$

to show that $659_2^{(2;t)} = 659(2^{12-t} - 1)(2^{12} - 1) \equiv 2131099 \pmod{11184810}$ is a Sierpiński number. Note here that $\ell = \lfloor \log_2 659 \rfloor + 1 = 10$. Similarly, when $t \equiv 1361 \pmod{2730}$, we can use

$$\begin{aligned} &\{(r_j, m_j, p_j) : 1 \leq j \leq 6\} \\ &= \{(1, 2, 3), (1, 3, 7), (0, 4, 5), (6, 8, 17), (2, 12, 13), (18, 24, 241)\} \end{aligned}$$

to show that $659_2^{(2;t)} \equiv 1639459 \pmod{11184810}$ is a Sierpiński number.

The next theorem will follow as a corollary to Theorems 4.3 and 4.6.

Theorem 4.4. *Let $t \equiv \mathfrak{t} \pmod{2730}$ for some $\mathfrak{t} \in \{1369, 2599\}$. Then $659_2^{(2;t)}$ is a 2-repstring Riesel number.*

We end this article with an interesting observation. From Theorems 3.5 and 3.6, when the repeating integer is 18107 in base-2 representation, the number of repetitions to get a Sierpiński number is congruent to 25 modulo 56, while the number of repetitions to get a Riesel number is congruent to 31 modulo 56. Notice that 25 and 31 are additive inverses modulo 56. Similarly, from Theorems 4.3 and 4.4, when the repeating integer is 659 in base-2 representation, the number of repetitions to get a Sierpiński number and the number of repetitions to get a Riesel number form additive inverses of each other, as $131 \equiv -2599 \pmod{2730}$ and $1361 \equiv -1369 \pmod{2730}$. Table 1, obtained computationally, establishes this observation in several other cases, and Theorem 4.6 confirms this observation.

Before presenting the theorem, we provide a useful lemma that is due to Filaseta and Harvey.

Lemma 4.5 ([10]). *Let a be an integer. If $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j}\}$ is a covering system, then $\mathcal{C}_a = \{r_j + a \pmod{m_j}\}$ is a covering system.*

Theorem 4.6. *Let k, \mathfrak{t} , and w be positive integers, and let z be a nonnegative integer. Then there exists a fixed covering system \mathcal{C} that produces $k_2^{(z;t)}$ as a Sierpiński number for all $t \equiv \mathfrak{t} \pmod{w}$ using the covering system method in Section 2 if and only if there exists a fixed covering system \mathcal{C}' that produces $k_2^{(z;t')}$ as a Riesel number for all $t' \equiv -\mathfrak{t} \pmod{w}$ using the covering system method in Section 2.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C} = \{r_j \pmod{m_j}\}$ be the covering system that produces $k_2^{(z;t)}$ as a Sierpiński number for all $t \equiv \mathfrak{t} \pmod{w}$. Further, let p_j be a primitive prime divisor

k	z	Sierpiński condition	Riesel condition
659	2	$t \equiv 131 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 2599 \pmod{2730}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 2131099 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 762701 \pmod{11184810}$
		$t \equiv 1361 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 1369 \pmod{2730}$
727	2	$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 1639459 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 1254341 \pmod{11184810}$
		$t \equiv 127 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 2603 \pmod{2730}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 3098059 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 10702091 \pmod{11184810}$
1177	4	$t \equiv 1507 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 1223 \pmod{2730}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 271129 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 2344211 \pmod{11184810}$
		$t \equiv 19 \pmod{84}$	$t' \equiv 65 \pmod{84}$
1189	1	$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 84319681 \pmod{140100870}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 95997337 \pmod{140100870}$
		$t \equiv 1159 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 1571 \pmod{2730}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 7523281 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 4384979 \pmod{11184810}$
1549	1	$t \equiv 2059 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 671 \pmod{2730}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 7400371 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 4507889 \pmod{11184810}$
		$t \equiv 38 \pmod{1365}$	$t' \equiv 1327 \pmod{1365}$
1747	1	$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 32552687 \pmod{209191710}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 23909173 \pmod{209191710}$
		$t \equiv 1343 \pmod{1365}$	$t' \equiv 22 \pmod{1365}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 198067007 \pmod{209191710}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 67586563 \pmod{209191710}$
18107	0	$t \equiv 307 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 2423 \pmod{2730}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 4573999 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 5049251 \pmod{11184810}$
		$t \equiv 397 \pmod{2730}$	$t' \equiv 2333 \pmod{2730}$
26267	0	$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 7892569 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 1730681 \pmod{11184810}$
		$t \equiv 25 \pmod{56}$	$t' \equiv 31 \pmod{56}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 8007257 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 10702091 \pmod{11184810}$
32681	0	$t \equiv 9 \pmod{56}$	$t' \equiv 47 \pmod{56}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 1624097 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 1730681 \pmod{11184810}$
		$t \equiv 51 \pmod{56}$	$t' \equiv 5 \pmod{56}$
		$k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv 4067003 \pmod{11184810}$	$k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 6610811 \pmod{11184810}$

Table 1: Sierpiński 2-repstrings and Riesel 2-repstrings

of $2^{m_j} - 1$ such that $k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv -2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ for each j . Note that $\mathcal{C}' = \{r_j + (z + \ell)t \pmod{m_j}\}$ is a covering system by Lemma 4.5, and we claim that \mathcal{C}' produces $k_2^{(z;t')}$ as a Riesel number for all $t' \equiv -t \pmod{w}$.

If $2^{z+\ell} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$ for some j , then $kt \equiv k_2^{(z;t)} \equiv -2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ for all $t \equiv t \pmod{w}$. In other words, $k(qw + t) \equiv -2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ for all integers q . Hence, $k(-qw - t) \equiv 2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j}$ for all integers q , thus $k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv kt' \equiv 2^{-r_j} \equiv 2^{-(r_j + (z+\ell)t)} \pmod{p_j}$ for all $t' \equiv -t \pmod{w}$.

It remains to show that $k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv 2^{-(r_j + (z+\ell)t)} \pmod{p_j}$ when $2^{z+\ell} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$. Note that $k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p_j}$ since $k_2^{(z;t)}$ is a multiple of k and $-2^{-r_j} \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p_j}$. Further note that $2^{(z+\ell)w} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$, which can be deduced from the congruence $k_2^{(z;w+t)} \equiv -2^{-r_j} \equiv k_2^{(z;t)} \pmod{p_j}$. Hence, $k_2^{(z;t')} \equiv k_2^{(z;w-t)} \pmod{p_j}$. The proof

of the claim is completed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_2^{(z;t)} &= k \frac{2^{(z+\ell)t} - 1}{2^{z+\ell} - 1} \equiv -2^{-r_j} \pmod{p_j} \\
 k \frac{2^{(z+\ell)t} - 1}{2^{z+\ell} - 1} \cdot \frac{2^{(z+\ell)(w-t)} - 1}{2^{(z+\ell)t} - 1} &\equiv -2^{-r_j} \cdot \frac{2^{(z+\ell)(w-t)} - 1}{2^{(z+\ell)t} - 1} \pmod{p_j} \\
 k \frac{2^{(z+\ell)(w-t)} - 1}{2^{z+\ell} - 1} &\equiv -2^{-r_j} \cdot \frac{2^{(z+\ell)(w-t)} - 1}{2^{(z+\ell)t} - 1} \cdot \frac{2^{(z+\ell)t}}{2^{z+\ell}} \pmod{p_j} \\
 k_2^{(z;w-t)} &\equiv -2^{-r_j} \cdot \frac{2^{(z+\ell)w} - 2^{(z+\ell)t}}{(2^{(z+\ell)t} - 1)2^{(z+\ell)t}} \pmod{p_j} \\
 k_2^{(z;w-t)} &\equiv -2^{-r_j} \cdot \frac{1 - 2^{(z+\ell)t}}{(2^{(z+\ell)t} - 1)2^{(z+\ell)t}} \pmod{p_j} \\
 k_2^{(z;w-t)} &\equiv -2^{-r_j} \cdot (-2^{-(z+\ell)t}) \pmod{p_j} \\
 k_2^{(z;w-t)} &\equiv 2^{-(r_j+(z+\ell)t)} \pmod{p_j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof of the converse follows in a similar fashion. □

Corollary 4.7. *The answers κ and κ' to Questions 1.3 and 1.6, respectively, are equal to each other. Similarly, the answers $\tilde{\kappa}$ and $\tilde{\kappa}'$ to Questions 4.1 and 4.2, respectively, are also equal to each other.*

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